

Kauthuvam: Textual References And Interpretations

Vanidas Chakingal

Independent Researcher

Abstract:

Kauthuvam is an invocatory item in Bharatanāṭyam recitals. It is a hymn, a song of devotion in praise of a deity. It was said to be performed by the devādasi as part of the daily rituals, on special occasions during the festivals. It was initially used to invoke blessings and create a spiritual atmosphere for the performance. This article is a study of Kauthuvam and its evolution, from the history of Kauthuvam to devadāsi tradition, where the reference is taken from Nityasumaṅgalī and an effort is made to find the relevance of Kauthuvam in the older times with the help of reference text like Cilappatikāram and Tolkāppiyam.

Keywords: Kauthuvam, Bharatanatyam, Nityasumangali, Tanjore Quartet, Dance Forms.

Introduction

The Tanjore Quartet transformed customary Kauthuvam-s into formal musical pieces, presenting the literary and artistic styles of the 19th-century. The evolution of Kauthuvam, can be traced through its representation in early literary texts and its transformation into a significant element of modern performance culture. Some traditional motifs, like invocations of āstadikpālās were retained, but the emphasis shifted to aesthetic appeal. Kauthuvam combines rhythmic syllables (Jati-s) with poetic verses (sāhithyam). Over time, Kauthuvam-s evolved from being a part of rituals to becoming an invocatory piece in most Katcheris.^{1 2}

This article is a study of Kauthuvam and its evaluation, from the history of Kauthuvam to devadāsi tradition, where the reference is taken from Nityasumaṅgalī and an effort is made to find the relevance of Kauthuvam in the older times with the help of reference text like Cilappatikāram and Tolkāppiyam.

Tolkāppiyam represents early theoretical frameworks from the pre-Saṅgam or Saṅgam period, emphasizing the poetic structure and the rhythmic aspect which may have

¹ Āstadikpālās- guardians of directions.(Rao, V. D. N)

² Katcheri - is an hour or more that an hour-long program performed with a combination of classical dance items in a row one after the other following a format or a theme.

influenced the foundational aspects of Kauthuvam. Tolkāppiyam provides insights into the societal norms, aesthetic principles, and cultural practices followed. Its exploration of Pāḍāṇṭinai (themes of praise and eulogy) aligns with the performative and devotional aspects of Kauthuvam-s. Cilappatikāram, with its cultural and historical relevance, offers a valid perspective on the post-Saṅgam era. The text contextualizes dance as a part of temple rituals and societal customs, highlighting its significance in worship, festivals, and royal court settings. Though it does not explicitly reference Kauthuvam, the text illustrates the foundational elements of Tamil performing arts, including rhythm (tāla), expression (abhinaya), and the invocation of divine or protective spirits (Pūtam-s). The invocation of guardian spirits and the ritualistic performances described in the text hint at parallels with the thematic essence of Kauthuvam. Nityasumaṅgalī establishes a connection between Kauthuvam-s and their ritualistic and spiritual origins, while also tracing their evolution into performance art within the Bharatanāṭyam repertoire. It bridges the gap between historical practices and modern adaptations. The poetic format in Tolkāppiyam, ritualistic content in Cilappatikāram, and performativity as an invocation piece in Nityasumaṅgalī marks a significant reason for choosing these 3 texts as part of this study.

1. Tolkāppiyam

Tolkāppiyam is one of the oldest Tamil grammar texts, attributed to Tolkāppiyar. The text covers grammar, phonetics, syntax, morphology, semantics, and poetics, as well as aspects of society and culture. The text comprises three books, athikārams, which are further divided into multiple chapters (iyal-s) and sections (noorpā-s). The first section is called Eḷuttatikāram with 483 verses dealing with the system of the Tamil alphabet in its spoken and written modes, production, and articulation of speech sound in Tamil.³ The second section is called Collattikāram which comprises 463 verses based on morphology and syntax with the study of parts of speech in Tamil. The two sections together constitute a scientifically structured grammar of the Tamil language. The third section is titled Poruḷatikāram which contains 656 verses, the materials of literature, literary theories, theory of manifest emotion, mode of comparison, method of literary scholarship, and outline of natural history. Poruḷatikāram delves into cultural richness, defining how literature reflects the societal values and emotional nuances of life.⁴In

³ Eḷuttatikāram - orthography (Muruga, V - Structure, organization and content of Tolkāppiyam).

⁴ Poruḷatikāram (Muruga, V - Structure, organization and content of Tolkāppiyam).

Poruḷatikāram there is a component known as Pāḍāṅṭiṅai which refers to the classification of warfare and battlefields in Tamil society. It mainly deals with the content and meaning of Tamil literature, particularly the themes and settings of puṛam poetry.⁵

The Kauthuvam referred to in Nityasumaṅgalī and Cilappatikāram aligns with the praise of deities, whereas in Tolkāppiyam it is associated with court culture. There are relevant lines praising the king or the emperor, who is considered as a presiding deity of the kingdom and is worshiped with utmost devotion.

In Tolkāppiyam- Pāḍāṅṭiṅai, it is stated that the praise is sung on the following occasions.

*“tāvin nal icai karutiya kiṭantōrkku
cūtar ēttiya tuyileṭai nilaiyum;
kūttarum, pāṇarum, porunarum, viṛaliyum
ārriṭaik kāṭci uṛaḷat tōṅṛri,
perṛa peru vaḷam peṛārkkku aṛivurū,
ceṅru payaṅ etirac coṅṇa pakkamum;
ciraṅta nāḷiṅil ceṅṛam nīkki,
piṛanta nāḷvayin perumaṅkalamum;
ciraṅta cīrtti maṅṇumaṅkalamum;
naṭai mikuttu ēttiya kuṭai niḷal marapum;
māṅārc cuṭṭiya vāḷmaṅkalamum;
maṅ eyil aḷitta maṅṇumaṅkalamum;
paricil kaṭaiiya kaṭaikkūṭtu nilayum;
perṛa piṅṅarum peru vaḷaṅ ētti
naṭaivayin tōṅṛiya iru vakai viṭaiyum
accamum uvakaiyum eccam iṅṛi,
nāḷum puḷḷum piṛavaṛriṅ nimittamum;
kālam kaṅṇiya oṃpatai uḷappaṭa
ṅāḷattu varūum naṭakkaiyattu kuṛippin*

⁵ Puṛam - themes related to external life. (Murugan, V - Tolkāppiyam as a world classic)

*kālam mūnroṭu kaṇṇiya varumē.*⁶

The above lines from Pāḍāṇṭai illustrate how the king's life is glorified. Emphasising the necessity of singing specific songs to awaken him, accompany various ceremonies throughout his day or life, and perform bedtime rituals to ensure his sleep. This is very similar to the songs mentioned as part of nityarcanā in Nityasumaṅgalī, where the day begins with Melukolupu which is sung around 4am as a wake-up call for the lord, and the day concludes with lāli and ūñjal as bedtime rituals.

The invocation of Pūtam-s (guardian spirits) in Cilappatikāram is similar to the hymns in the court, as they intend to create harmony, protection, and prosperity. These compositions praise deities or significant figures, invoking their blessings for auspicious beginnings. Similarly, hymns sung in the royal court serve as invocations to underline the god-like attributes of the king and to consecrate the process of royalty. These protector spirits represent the metaphysical reality of protection for the land just as the king is the earthly protector. Such compositions were not only celebratory but also helped reinforce the position of the king as a divine representative and moral protector of the realm. Ārupaṭai culture provided an environment where bards and minstrels, in addition to praising the king, directed other artists to him as a source of generosity. Hence, a very vibrant ecosystem of artistic exchange thrives at the hub of the king. Just like Kauthuvam-s held at the beginning of religious or festive occasions to present auspiciousness, hymns in court played ritualistic marks of importance in the life of the king. Ōmpaṭai hymns, which focus specifically upon omens and blessings, follow the Kauthuvam tradition, invoking deities for the land's protection and blessings, Tamil literature and music, therefore, ensure a linguistic and cultural heritage.

1.1. Symbolism and Metaphor

Kauthuvam celebrates deities, virtues, strength, and grace, often linking them to protection and prosperity. In the Tolkāppiyam hymns, elements like Vālmaṅkalam (praising the sword) and Kuṭainilaivālttu (praising the umbrella), similarly celebrate

⁶ Murugan, Vellayagounder, editor. Tolkāppiyam: Text (with Non-metrical Segmentation), Transliteration and Translations in English Verse and Prose. Translated by Vellayagounder Murugan, Central Institute of Classical Tamil, 2021.(Pg: 574)

the king's power, his role as a protector, and his ability to maintain prosperity. It is the custom of Kauthuvam-s to show gods as even-handed administrators and maintainers of the cosmos. In the same way, the kings in Tolkāppiyam hymns present themselves as balanced and gracious rulers maintaining the order of welfare. Both Kauthuvam and the hymns express the same purpose but in different contexts. The Navasandhi in Nītyasumaṅgalī, the invocation of Pūtam-s in Cilappatikāram, and Ōmpatai in Tolkāppiyam are all done with a purpose to ward off the evil and to sanctify the space for the auspicious proceedings where in the former part the deity is referred as the central figure of importance and in the latter it is the King who is considered as the lord.

2. Cilappatikāram

Cilappatikāram was written by Iḷaṅkōvaṭikaḷ and is considered one of the five great Tamil epics (Aimperumkāppiyaṅkaḷ).⁷ The story revolves around two main characters, Kōvalaṅ who is a wealthy merchant's son, and Kaṅṅaki his virtuous wife. Kōvalaṅ falls in love with a dancer named Mādhavi, who squanders his wealth. Kōvalaṅ realizes his mistake and returns to Kaṅṅaki and they move to Maturai to rebuild their lives. They decide to sell Kaṅṅaki's anklet and start a new life with the money they get from it. Kōvalaṅ wrongly gets accused of stealing the queen's anklet and gets executed by the Paṇḍaya King. Kaṅṅaki proves her husband's innocence and, in her grief and anger, curses the city of Maturai, leading to its destruction by fire. A unique feature of this epic is that the story's central figure and hero is a woman, Kaṅṅaki.

The epic is divided into three Kāṇḍams (books) comprising 30 cantos (Kāthais)⁸. In the first book Pukārkkāṇḍam in canto 3 which is Araṅkeru kāthai there is a detailed description of the stage and that it had four pillars which was erected as an offering to the four demigods. Before any performance, these gods were invoked for the successful completion of the program. It was believed that the existence of these four demigods (pootham) was necessary for the land or the village to be fertile and prosperous.

⁷ Aimperumkāppiyaṅkaḷ - five Tamil epics according to later Tamil literary tradition. They are Cilappatikāram, Manimekalai, Cīvaka Cintāmaṇi, Valayapathi and Kundalakesi. (prabatamilthend)

⁸ Kāthai - means stories in Tamil.

- Andhana Pūtam represents divine energies associated with ascetics, hermits, and spiritual pursuits. It signifies wisdom, penance, and the transcendental aspect of human life.
- Arasa Pūtam is linked to kings and governance. Symbolizes justice, power, and the administration of dharma (righteousness) in society.
- Vāṇika Pūtam pertains to merchants and trade. Represents prosperity, wealth, and the economic lifeline of the community.
- Velan Pūtam is associated with agricultural and rural communities, particularly cowherds and farmers. It reflects fertility, sustenance, and the symbiotic relationship between humans and nature.

*“eḷukōl akalattu eṅkōll nīlattu
orukōl uyarattu uruppiṇaitu āki
uttarap palakaiyoṭu arankiṅ palakai
vaitta iṭainilam nār̥kōl āka
ēṛra vāyil iraṇṭuṭaṅ poliyat
tōrriya arankil toḷutaṅar ēttap
pūtarai eḷuti mēlnilai vaittut”*

There is a detailed explanation of the preparation of the Araṅgam for presenting the dance-drama. To measure the stage, the texts recommended a bamboo rod- the distance of a span between the two joints, and twenty-four thumbs long- from the sacred hills.⁹ The stage was eight rods long, seven deep, and one high. It had two grand doors, conveniently located. Four rods was the distance between the crossbeams and the platform. Images of demigods, placed above the stage, were worshiped and raised. The meticulously built stage reflects the cultural and spiritual importance of the performance. The Araṅgam is more than a performance space, it is a sacred venue where art meets spirituality, symbolizing the cosmic balance between dharma (righteousness) and karma (actions). The demigods praised here are very similar to the invocation of good, similar to the invocation performed in balidāna in Nityasumaṅgalī.

In canto 6, Mādhavi Kaṭalāṭṭu kāthai states

⁹ Araṅgam - performance stage

*“māyōṅ pāṇiyum varuṇap pūtar
nālvakai pāṇiyum nalamperu koḷkai
vānūr matiyamum pātip piṅṅarc”*¹⁰

The above verse from Cilappatikāram can be interpreted as the invocation of the four Varuṇa Pūtam-s in a symbolic context. Māyōṅ refers to Lord Kṛṣṇa and Varuṇa pūtar the divine energies (pūtar) of Varuṇa, the god of rain and water. This highlights Kṛṣṇa’s association with nature and the protective forces of Varuṇa Pūtam-s. Nālvakai pāṇiyum refers to the four-fold cosmic or societal functions represented by the four Varuṇa Pūtam-s. These energies work harmoniously to maintain the welfare (nalamperu koḷkai) of the world. Vānūr matiyamum pātip piṅṅarc refers to the connection between heavenly wisdom (Vānūr matiyam) and its implementation in earthly life (pātip piṅṅarc). It signifies the king’s divine mandate to uphold justice and dharma in alignment with cosmic principles. In the eleven dances performed by Mādhavi in the Indra vizha, the performance starts with Mādhavi offering prayers through song and dance, to Māyōṅ, to the four orders of spiritual choir, and to the beneficent moon, sky wanderer. Mādhavi is said to have performed 11 dances which include Alliyam, Kodukotti, Kudaj, Kudam, Pēdi, Kadayam, Pāṇḍaraṅgam, Mal, Tudi, Marakkal, and Pāvai. Many of these dance forms are associated with gods and deities such as Śiva, Muruga, Kāma, Durga, Kṛṣṇa, Lakśmi, and Indrani.

In Cilappatikāram there was a practice to worship the four Pūtam-s before the commencing of the actual program, this was done to sustain the happiness and prosperity of the place. The people also believed that it was mandatory to worship the four Pūtam-s and it was more of a ritual than an invocation. In Cilappatikāram there is also a mention of four pillar-like structures built as part of the Araṅgam and four demigods placed above it as protectors. Hence it can be related that the four demigods must have been placed in four cardinal points. Worshipping and invoking them before the commencing of the actual program brought them good luck and auspiciousness. The worship of four Varuṇa Pūtam-s in Cilappatikāram and the worship of nine gods -

¹⁰ Iṅkōvaṭikal. Cilappatikāram: Text, Transliteration and Translation in English Verse and Prose. Edited by K. Chellappan, translated by Rajagopal Parthasarathy, et al., Central Institute of Classical Tamil, 2021. (Pg: 139)

Navasandhi, in Nityasumaṅgalī, is done with the same intentions to sanctify the place and bring in good aura. As the purpose and intent of the item in both the places are same and even though the name of the ritual is not known there is the possibility that the performance on the four demigods was nothing, but the Kauthuvam. Even though the text does not explicitly use the term Kauthuvam, with the above analysis we may conclude that the worshipping of the demigods was not named as Kauthuvam but was actually serving the same purpose and ritual importance as Kauthuvam.

Canto 22 from Cilappatikāram conveys that if the guardian spirits are dissatisfied they will leave the kingdom. The loss of each of the several spirits corresponds to a weakening of at least one key social pillar, justice, economy, and culture. This mass withdrawal points out that when at least some rulers depart from righteousness, even their divine protectors will leave their positions, thereby rendering the land susceptible to large destruction. Kauthuvam was performed to prevent such occurrences by invoking the good spirits to protect and serve as a guardian.

2.1. Symbolism and Metaphor

In Cilappatikāram, while the term Kauthuvam isn't explicitly mentioned, the idea of invoking divine beings through dance is closely related to the descriptions of the four Pūtam-s. The Pūtam-s reinforce the Tamil worldview of divine forces guiding human existence, as seen in the deification of Kaṇṇaki in Vañcikkāṇḍam. Arasa Pūtam comes into focus when the Paṇḍya king fails to uphold justice by wrongly accusing Kōvalaṅ of theft. His failure to align with the ideals of dharma leads to his downfall and the destruction of Maturai. Andhana Pūtam and Arasa Pūtam are evident in the depiction of King Ceṅkuṭṭuvaṅ, who demonstrates spiritual wisdom and royal justice. The four Pūtam-s collectively represent the balance of spiritual, administrative, economic, and rural life. There appears to be a link between this practice and the modern Kauthuvam, which is performed to invoke and celebrate deities, usually at the start of temple rituals or performances. Even in the modern day, Kauthuvam-s are performed as an invocatory item which is based on celebrating a particular deity sung and danced in praise of that deity, post which the actual performance starts, though the significance is not as same as sanctifying the space, it remains as an invocation. Although Cilappatikāram does not specifically refer to these

invocations as Kauthuvam-s, the purpose of performing the sanctifying process remains in sync with the purpose of Kauthuvam-s.

3. Nityasumaṅgalī

The book ‘Nityasumaṅgalī: Devadāsi Tradition in South India by Saskia C. Kersenboom’ provides a detailed exploration of the devadāsi tradition, its historical context, cultural significance, and transformation over time. The book examines the historical development of the devadāsi system through three main periods:

- The classical and late classical Tamil culture (100 BCE –600 CE)
- The medieval period of Hinduism (600 CE –1600 CE)
- The Tanjore court culture and subsequent changes (1600 CE –1947 CE).

These sections highlight how the devadāsi role evolved with temple rituals and patronage systems during these periods. During the devadāsi tradition, dance and music were a central part of temple worship and festivals.¹¹ The highlight of Kauthuvam according to Nityasumaṅgalī is that it was traditionally performed not as a mere entertainment but as an integral component of temple rituals. The ritual of balidāna, involved offerings made to appease spirits and ward off negative energies. The performance of Kauthuvam-s during this ritual symbolized a cleansing act, both physical and metaphysical, preparing the sacred space for the main festival. Kauthuvam-s were believed to purify the ritual space by driving away evil spirits and creating a protective boundary.

In the first chapter of Nityasumaṅgalī, ‘Devadāsi of South India’ the Cola period, began with the coronation of Rajaraja in 985 A.D. and lasted till 1279 A.D., when Rajendra III was defeated by the Paṇḍya forces. In the famous inscription of the Tanjore Bṛhadiśvara temple (South Indian Inscriptions Vol. II, No. 66) a detailed account of the number of employees and their remuneration is given. It also mentions the transfer of 400 dancing girls from several temples to the new temple. The chapter mentions the terms used for the offering of dances, which can be identified based on their place within the structure of temple ritual. One such example, found in Nityasumaṅgalī, is “cantikkuṇippam” which refers to dances performed at the nine

¹¹ Nityasumaṅgalī is referred to as an ever-auspicious woman. (Kersenboom Pg:47)

cardinal points (sandhi) on the temple ground. This form of dance may have later evolved into what is known as Navasandhi Kauthuvam, with a possible variant called cantikūttu.¹² This indicates that the Kauthuvam was performed during the Cola period as part of temple tradition.

Fig 2: Image depiction drawing synonymity between Cantikkunippam and Navasandhi Kauthuvam

Cantikkunippam is said to be a dance performed in nine cardinal points—center, east, south-east, south, south-west, west, north-west, north, and north-east. Each direction is associated with a specific deity, which is also seen in Navasandhi Kauthuvam, where the corresponding deities for each direction are Brahma, Indra, Agni, Yama, Nirudhi, Varuṇa, Vāyu, kubēra, and Isāna. They are performed in nine different rāga-s and tāla-s known collectively as the navasandhi tālas, and are said to have been performed in nine different directions. The navasandhi dance was usually performed during the dhvajārohana, the first day of Brahmotsavam in temples.¹³ During the period of the Tanjore Quartet, the performance of these dances became a regular feature in temple rituals. Detailed description of Navasandhi Kauthuvam and Pañcamūrti Kauthuvam are found in the text Ādi Bharata Kalā Mañjari, including the notations and sāhithyam for each sandhi, along with the corresponding rāga and tāla in which each Kauthuvam is to be rendered. These aspects are further elaborated in Chapter 4.

¹² Kersenboom, Saskia C. Nityasumangali: Devādasi Tradition in South India. 2011, ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA0719582X.(Pg 24-29)

¹³ The term "Dhvajārohana" translates to "hoisting the flag," and it refers to the ritualistic raising of a flag or a banner (dhvajā) on a pole (dhvajā stambha) within a temple precinct or during festivals.(Kersenboom Pg: 108)

In the period of Tanjore courts and the subsequent developments till independence, a new dynasty of Marata descent established itself in Tanjore in 1676. During this period systematization of the art of dance was done by the four brothers Chinnaya, Ponnaya, Śivānandam, and Vadivēlu who were later known as the Tanjore Quartets. They, along with Muttusvami Diksitar, devised a basic course for dance training and composed a balanced consort repertoire. They also created several dance compositions exclusively for temple rituals, known as Kauthuvam (kavitva - Poem), which were performed in honor of various Gods. One such item is Pañcamūrti Kauthuvam, which is based on five Gods namely Vināyaka, Murugan, Sambandar, Candikeśvara and Naṭāraja. Another example is Navasandhi Kauthuvam, performed for the gods associated with the nine cardinal points of the temple ground- namely Brahma, Indra, Agni, Yama, Nirudhi, Varuṇa, Vāyu, kubēra, and Íśāna.¹⁴

Similarly, in the discussion on the topic, ‘similarities of village cults’, there is a mention of an important ritual shared by both the village and the temple: the custom of propitiating the evil spirits and forces that reside within the ritual territory. This must be performed before the start of the festival (utsava) on a smaller scale each day during the festival, and almost symbolically as part of the daily worship (nityotsava).¹⁵ ¹⁶ This ritual is called balidāna (gift of bali - sacrifice onto the balipath) among the village cults.¹⁷ It was performed by offering rice with kumkum and a fluid milk product, accompanied by the suitable mantra (ritual formula), beating of the drums, and sometimes with other instruments and a short dance. The specifics of the ritual varied depending on the deity that is propitiated. These dance pieces can be equated as Kauthuvam-s and were danced by the devadāsi in the 19th Century. The custom was forgotten during the 20th century and only fragments were preserved.

The temple repertoire followed by devadāsi, mentioned in Nityasumaṅgalī for daily ritual (Nityārcanā), is as follows:

¹⁴ Kersenboom, Saskia C. Nityasumaṅgalī: Devādasi Tradition in South India. 2011, ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA0719582X. (Pg 38-44)

¹⁵ Utsava (Sanskrit: उत्सव, lit. 'special occasion') also referred to as Utsavam, generally means a festival or celebration or any joyous occasion, mostly associated with Hinduism.(Kersenboom Pg: 61)

¹⁶ Nityotsava - celebration on a daily basis, a smaller scale or each day of the festival.(Kersenboom Pg: 61)

¹⁷ Balidāna - gift of bali or sacrifice made as part of the festival.(Kersenboom Pg: 108)

Fig 3: Daily rituals performed in a devadāsi repertoire.

“Some devadāsi remembered the custom of ‘showing some hands’ during the balidāna ritual. Two such Kauthuvam-s have been preserved: the navasandhi Kauthuvam and Pañcamūrthi Kauthuvam which received their choreography from the dance masters of Tanjore court.”¹⁸

The Nityārcanā, daily ritual for the Lord as documented in Nityasumaṅgalī, starts with the Mēlukolupu which is sung around 4 am and is considered a wake-up call for the lord. The song describes the morning call of the rooster, the blooming of flowers, and various other scenarios that are related to early morning, asking the Lord to wake up from his sleep.¹⁹ This is followed by Pakalu Vināyaka Stōtram which is

¹⁸ Kersenboom, Saskia C. Nityasumaṅgalī: Devādasi Tradition in South India. 2011, ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA0719582X. (Pg: 61)

¹⁹ Nityārcanā - daily ritual followed in the temple at specific times connecting the daily ritual of the deity.(Kersenboom Pg: 106)

sung during the worship of the shrines around the central sanctum in the mid-morning around 11:00 am. The song praises lord Vināyaka by highlighting his features and attributes. Puṣpāñjali on Śaṅmukha follows the vināyaka stótram which is performed as a conclusion to the offering of the kumbhadīpa (pot-lamp) at 6:00 pm. This is followed by Nritta items, which may include puṣpāñjali or Kauthuvam, with a combination of jati and sāhithyam. The nityārcanā concludes with lāli and ūñjal, performed at 9:00 pm as a bedtime ritual in the bed chamber.

3.1. Symbolism and Metaphor

Kauthuvam-s in general evoke the emotion of bhakti. The performance of Kauthuvam-s, particularly during rituals like balidāna or the commencement of festivals, is metaphorically seen as an act of cleansing. Kauthuvam-s often praise the deity's qualities, such as justice, protection, and strength, symbolizing the ideal ruler's attributes in Tamil culture. In the documentation of temple repertoire by the devadāsi under the subheading Nritta I and II, there is a mention of choreographies which has a specific language called as corkaṭṭu which reveals the composition should be performed exclusively in a ritually pure place, and by an initiated performer.²⁰ There are also specifically designated corkaṭṭu used like taku, tonka. This feature is shared by the Puṣpāñjali nritta, Navasandhi, and Pañcamūrti Kauthuvam, and it also states that these compositions never occur in the so-called Catir katcheri but are performed by the devadāsi only with the observance of ritual restrictions.²¹

- *Relevance of Puṣpāñjali notation and Gaṇapati Kauthuvam jati*

Puṣpāñjali notation as mention in Nityasumaṅgalī is as follows.

“*nṛtta I (pure dance)*”

<i>ta</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>tōñ</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>di</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>tōñ</i>	<i>ka</i>
<i>ta ku</i>	<i>tōñ ka</i>	<i>di ku</i>	<i>tōñ ka</i>	<i>ta</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>di ku</i>	<i>tōñ</i>
<i>ta</i>	<i>teyñku</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>ni</i>	<i>tō</i>	<i>ta tey</i>	<i>yuñka</i>	<i>tōñ ka</i>
<i>di ku</i>	<i>tā</i>	<i>tey</i>	...				

²⁰ Corkaṭṭu or Sollukaṭṭu is a phrase of rhythmic syllables linked to specific units of dance movement.

²¹ Catir katcheri - dance concert performed by devadāsi-s on a stage.

Puṣpāñjali Śloka:

*kalhāūra hāra kalitāmarā puṣpapūr ṇa
svarnābja pattra navaratna vicitravarṇam
phulla(ra) vṛnda navahallaka pūjītūya
puṣpāñjalir bhavatum(ē) śikhi vāhanāya.”²²*

Gaṇapati Kauthuvam jati as mentioned in the reference from the academy of Ghungroo is as follows:

*“Tha dhigi dhigi thai dhi dhi thai dhi dhi dha tha thi dha tha thaham || 2 ||
Dha tha nutha kita kina thonga dhikuthom thonga
Nam kita kita thaka nam kita kita thaka nam kita kitathaka dheemtha
Nutha kita kina thonga dhikuthom thonga
Nam kita kita thaka nam kita kita thaka nam kita kitathaka dheemtha
Tha ham dhi tham dhi kita thaka dhi dhi tham tha tha duruguduthari
Nam kita kita thaka nam kita kita thaka nam kita kitathaka dheemtha || 2 ||
Thaku deku thakita nam kita kita thaka denam tha dhi dhi tha || 2 ||
Tha dhari dhanam dhana tha hatha kita thaka jhum tarikita jhum dhi thakumtha riku
dhana || 2 ||
Dhanam dhanatha jhanum jhanutha dhimim dhimitha tha tha dhi dhi dhi tha tha
hathath tha
Dha kita jhum thari jhe kita jhum thari
Thalangu tha dhith thaka thadhi gina thom || 3 ||”²³*

From the above notations of jati in the Gaṇapati Kauthuvam and Puṣpāñjali mentioned in devadāsi repertoire, a striking similarity in rhythmic syllables can be observed. In Puṣpāñjali, the corkaṭṭus with syllables such as ‘taku tōṅka’ and ‘diku tōṅka’ are mentioned, while in Gaṇapati Kauthuvam, syllables like ‘Nutha kita kina thonga’ appear, showcasing the shared rhythmic pattern. There is also a structural similarity between the compositions. In Puṣpāñjali, a jati is followed by a puṣpāñjali sloka, while in Gaṇapati Kauthuvam as done today, a jati is followed by sāhithyam. While Puṣpāñjali is considered an opening piece, invoking divine blessings and

²² Puṣpāñjali notation - (Kersenboom Pg: 154)

²³ Academy, Ghungroo.

symbolically offering flowers to the deity, Kauthuvam is often followed by adding a narrative dimension with a focus on the glorification of the deity. The rhythmic and lyrical parallels between these items highlight the enduring legacy of the devadāsi repertoire and its transition from temple to stage. This analysis suggests that Kauthuvam was included in the devadāsi repertoire other than the Navasandhi and Pañcamūrti Kauthuvam, under the classification as nritta, which grouped items like Puṣpāñjali and Kauthuvam. Though originally these were part of temple rituals, pieces like Gaṇapati Kauthuvam continue to be performed on stage today.

Conclusion

The study elaborates on Kauthuvam with reference to three major texts- Nityasumaṅgalī, Cilappatikāram, and Tolkāppiyam have been considered as the key source to understand the symbolic relevance of Kauthuvam. The invocatory piece, Cantikkuṇippam, performed on the nine cardinal points, is compared to the Navasandhi Kauthuvam, a dance mentioned in the devadāsi repertoire and performed on the nine gods associated with the nine directions, as explored in Nityasumaṅgalī. However, Kauthuvam is not explicitly mentioned in early Tamil epics such as Cilappatikāram or Tolkāppiyam. In Cilappatikāram, the chapter Araṅkeru kāthai, mentions the Varuṇa Pūtam-s, for whom pillars were erected and worshiped for the auspicious beginning and completion of a program. The four Varuṇa Pūtam-s act as the protector of the land and have similarities to the concept of Navasandhi Kauthuvam. The belief that failing to appease the Varuṇa Pūtam-s would result in the destruction of the land; this particular connection has been explored with Kaṇṇaki's story. Tolkāppiyam mentions hymns performed in court, by praising the king and also at occurrences like Ōmpatai, which were performed to ward off evil and negative energy. The creation of cosmic harmony and balance through the invocation of celestial energies cuts across all the Varuṇa Pūtam-s in Cilappatikāram, Navasandhi Kauthuvam in Nityasumaṅgalī, and the Ōmpatai in Tolkāppiyam. In all the three, there is a shared emphasis on the role of guardian spirits or deities in protecting ritual sanctity and social order.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Dr. Rajshri Ramakrishna, Professor and Head, Department of Indian Music, University of Madras, and Dr. Raguraman Sir for guiding me with the topic selection and through the process of taking this topic forward. Finally, I want to express my heartfelt thanks to my family, friends. Without the support and contributions of the people mentioned above, this research would not have been possible.

References

Books

1. Kersenboom, Saskia C. *Nityasumāṅgalī: Devadāsi Tradition in South India*. 2011, ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA0719582X
2. S, Seetha. *Tanjore as a Seat of Music during the 17th, 18th, and 19th centuries*. 2001.
3. Murugan, Vellayagounder, editor. *Tolkāppiyam: Text (with Non-metrical Segmentation), Transliteration and Translations in English Verse and Prose*. Translated by Vellayagounder Murugan, Central Institute of Classical Tamil, 2021.
4. *Iḷaṅkōvaṭikaḷ. Cilappatikaram: Text, Transliteration and Translation in English Verse and Prose*. Edited by K. Chellappan, translated by Rajagopal Parthasarathy, et al., Central Institute of Classical Tamil, 2021.
5. Raghuraman, S. *History Of Tamiz's Dance*. Translated by Lakshmi Ramaswamy. 2014.

Journals/Articles

6. Burla, V.N. and M, RamaKṛṣṇan. (2024) *READING SILAPPADIKARAM IN THE CONTEMPORARY TIMES: A STUDY OF ITS PERFORMATIVE ASPECTS*, *Shodhkosh: Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*. Available at: <https://www.granthaalayahpublication.org/Arts-Journal/index.php/ShodhKosh>

Web Sources

7. Parathasarthy, T.S and Visweswaran, Chitra. “Kavutuvam”, accessed April 4, 2025, <http://www.carnatica.net/special/kavuttuvam-tsp1.htm>.
8. Visweswaran, Chitra. *Kavuthvams*, accessed April 4, 2025, www.sahapedia.org/sites/default/files/Kavuthvams.pdf.
9. “Interview on Navasandhi Kauthuvam.” Spotify, 9 Sept. 2006, accessed April 4, 2025, open.spotify.com/track/0qlQMA0KdruQHJH41UVpoB.
10. *Articles - Kavuthuvams - Mallika Jayanthi*, accessed April 15, Available at: <https://narthaki.com/info/articles/art228.html>

11. Rao, V. D. N. "ESSENCE OF ASHTA DIKPAALAKAAS." Other Scripts by the same Author, accessed April 15, www.kamakoti.org/kamakoti/books/ESSENCE%20OF%20ASHTA%20DIKPAALAKAAS.pdf.
12. Academy, Ghungroo. "Vināyaka Kowthuvam Lyrics." Ghungroo Academy, 11 July 2024, accessed April 4, 2025, www.ghungrooacademy.com/post/Vināyaka-kowthuvam-lyrics.